

Figure S2. Serum proteins differentially expressed 1 and 2 h after OFC and at symptom onset relative to before OFC

Colored areas in the volcano plots show differentially expressed proteins upregulated and downregulated (A) 1 h after OFC, (B) 2 h after OFC, (C) at symptom onset relative to before OFC in the OFC-positive group and (D) 1 h after OFC and (E) 2 h relative to before OFC in the OFC-negative group. Proteome analysis of serum samples was performed using four biological replicates for the OFC-positive group and five biological replicates for the OFC-negative group.

(F) Venn diagram of upregulated proteins 2 h after OFC in the OFC-positive group (Serum-UpPOS2, Blue), 2 h after OFC in the OFC-negative group (Serum-UpNEG2, Green), and at symptom onset in the OFC-positive group (Serum-UpS, Red).